

**Socioeconomic Inequality and the Role of Parental Expectations in Track and
Subject-Level Placement in Irish Secondary Education**

Ilyar Heydari Barardehi¹, Yekaterina Chzhen¹, Jennifer E. Symonds², and Neil Kaye²

¹ Department of Sociology, Trinity College Dublin

² University College London, Social Research Institute, Institute of Education

Author Note

Ilyar Heydari Barardehi <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6068-2531>

Yekaterina Chzhen <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7437-2542>

Jennifer E. Symonds <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4259-6124>

Neil Kaye <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0994-626>

Correspondence regarding this article should be addressed to Ilyar Heydari Barardehi,

3 College Green, Trinity College Dublin, Dublin 2, Ireland.

Email: heydarii@tcd.ie

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Abstract

Socioeconomic status (SES) is a well-established determinant of educational outcomes. This study investigates the role of parental educational expectations (PEEs) in shaping socioeconomic disparities in academic trajectories in the Irish secondary education system. Drawing on longitudinal data from four waves of the Growing Up in Ireland (GUI '98) study, we assess whether early-age PEEs mediate the relationship between SES, i.e., household income and parental education, and students' academic track and subject-level placement in English and Mathematics. Measurements were taken at ages 9, 13, 17, and 20-years (original $N = 8,568$, longitudinal $N = 4,729$). Logistic and ordered logistic regression models, combined with Karlson–Holm–Breen (KHB) decomposition using bootstrapping, suggest that SES and PEEs independently and positively predict academic track and subject level placement. Moreover, PEEs act as important mediators for household income and parental education. However, at age 13, the mediation for education diminishes while the indirect effects of income grow more pronounced. These results underscore the enduring entangled roles of socioeconomic background and early parental expectations as mechanisms shaping students' educational outcomes.

Introduction

Parental educational expectations (PEEs) are widely recognised as a central influence on children's academic development. Beyond the provision of material resources, parents shape students' self-concept, motivation, and long-term aspirations by signalling the level of attainment they consider both possible and desirable (Pinguart & Ebeling, 2020; Yamamoto & Holloway, 2010). Unlike structural inequalities rooted in household income or parental education, PEEs are comparatively malleable and therefore represent a promising point of intervention for reducing educational disadvantage (Zhan & Sherraden, 2011). Building on sociological and psychological theories, this study examines how socioeconomic background shapes students' educational trajectories in Ireland, with a particular emphasis on the role of PEEs. Classic frameworks such as the Wisconsin Model of Status Attainment (Sewell et al., 1969) and value-transmission theories (Grusec & Goodnow, 1994) highlight parental expectations as a key mechanism through which family background is translated into children's academic pathways, underscoring their significance in both reproducing and potentially mitigating inequality.

Despite international evidence of the mediating role of parental educational expectations (PEEs) in linking socioeconomic status (SES) to children's educational outcomes, these dynamics remain insufficiently examined in the Irish context. Ireland's secondary system, while often described as comprehensive, incorporates subtle but consequential forms of differentiation through academic track choice and subject-level selection (Byrne & McCoy, 2017; Lucas, 2001). These decisions, such as pursuing Higher versus Ordinary or Foundation levels in Mathematics and English or choosing between academic and vocational Leaving Certificate pathways are closely tied to university eligibility and long-term opportunities. Research shows that students from lower-SES backgrounds are disproportionately channelled into vocational tracks and lower subject levels

(Smyth, 2018; Triventi et al., 2021). Yet what remains underexplored is how early parental expectations interact with SES in shaping these outcomes. Are parental expectations an independent driver of subject-level differentiation and track placement? Do they mediate the influence of parental background in long-term?

This study addresses these gaps and questions by drawing on the Growing Up in Ireland (GUI) longitudinal survey to establish the extent to which parental expectations may mediate the relationship between SES and students' educational choices. Using a lagged mediation framework, the analysis first examines whether expectations measured before critical branching points (ages 9 and 13) predict track placement and subject-level selection in English and Mathematics during the Senior Cycle of secondary education. Then it decomposes the association between SES, PEEs and student choices. Thus, the study addresses two questions: do SES and PEEs independently predict students' outcomes and do PEEs substantially mediate SES effects? In doing so, the research contributes both empirically and theoretically to debates on educational inequality, showing how family aspirations intersect with institutional structures to shape opportunity in Ireland's education system.

Background

Parental Educational Expectations and Educational Inequality

This study draws on key sociological and psychological frameworks to examine how socioeconomic background shapes students' academic trajectories in Ireland, with a particular focus on the role of parental educational expectations (PEEs). In this context, parents' educational expectations are conceptualised as *realistic aspirations*—distinct from idealistic hopes—in that they are more tightly constrained by institutional and structural barriers (Goldenberg et al. 2001; Finger, 2016). Such expectations are central to the intergenerational

transmission of advantage and inequality, operating within the broader institutional context of educational tracking and curricular differentiation (Gonzalez-Pienda et al., 2002).

A dominant strand in the literature views PEEs as a mediating mechanism through which family socioeconomic status (SES) influences students' academic outcomes. In this framework, higher family income, parental educational attainment, and richer home learning resources foster stronger and more aligned expectations, which in turn promote higher academic performance and access to advanced curricular tracks (Lai et al., 2022; Long & Pang, 2016). This perspective is formalised in the Wisconsin Model of Status Attainment (Sewell & Hauser, 1972), which positions parental expectations as a critical intermediary between family background and children's educational attainment. According to this model, parental expectations are shaped both by the family's socioeconomic environment and by children's early academic performance, and these expectations subsequently influence students' own aspirations, educational choices, and eventual outcomes.

Empirical studies lend strong support to this mechanism, showing that children from higher-SES families benefit from expectations that are more accurate, better aligned with their abilities, and more strongly reinforced within supportive home environments (Jacobs & Harvey, 2005; Chen & Gregory, 2010; Boone & van Houtte, 2013; Shi et al., 2023). By contrast, lower-income families often hold expectations that may be overly optimistic or overly pessimistic, thus misaligned with children's actual performance, which can impede effective decision-making about academic options (DeBacker & Routon, 2017; Alexander et al., 1994; Li & Chzhen, 2025). This process is closely aligned with Bourdieu's (2000) concept of *habitus*, whereby higher-SES parents internalise a set of dispositions informed by their own educational and occupational histories, enabling them to form more informed and realistic expectations. Such cultural capital shapes children's perceptions of what is attainable and channels them toward educational choices, particularly in high-stakes areas such as

mathematics, that align with long-term academic and career trajectories (Tan & Liu, 2022; Rimkute et al., 2012).

While the independent influence of parental educational expectations (PEEs) on student outcomes is well established (Pinquart & Ebeling, 2019), much of the current debate centres on the *extent* to which these expectations can account for, rather than simply coexist with, the broader effects of socioeconomic status (SES). Prior research shows that although PEEs exert a significant influence on students' attainment, often independently of family background and measured ability (Sewell & Shah, 1967; Li et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2016), they do not necessarily fully mediate the impact of structural socioeconomic inequalities. Despite mixed evidence on the magnitude of mediation, PEEs represent an important pathway through which parental education and resources shape academic outcomes (Li et al., 2020). Understanding the magnitude and persistence of PEEs' role in mediating SES is therefore crucial for identifying how far expectations can mitigate, rather than reproduce, existing social stratification in education.

Parental Expectations as a Precursor to Educational Outcomes

Parental educational expectations are widely understood to chronologically precede and shape children's academic outcomes, operating through a combination of socialisation processes and value formation mechanisms. Grusec and Goodnow's (1994) perception–acceptance pathway offers a useful framework for conceptualising this sequence. In the first stage, children must accurately recognise the values their parents hold; in the second, they must adopt these values as their own. Parental involvement in education, such as attending school meetings and events, discussing schoolwork, or providing educational resources can strongly influence both stages (Barni et al., 2011; Grolnick & Slowiaczek, 1994). These actions communicate the importance parents attach to schooling, while also reinforcing

emotional bonds and trust, which in turn increase the likelihood that children will internalise these values (Cheung & Pomerantz, 2012).

A complementary experience pathway extends this argument by suggesting that parents influence children's attitudes to education not only through explicit communication of values but also through the learning experiences they facilitate (Cheung & Pomerantz, 2015). Engaging children in conversations about the usefulness of education or encouraging persistence in completing assignments can lead them to assign greater importance to achievement, even without conscious recognition of parental beliefs (Hill & Tyson, 2009). Drawing on Bem's (1972) self-perception theory, the time and effort invested in academic tasks may also lead children to conclude that they must value education highly, reinforcing their commitment to learning.

Both frameworks emphasize that valuing achievement is a critical driver of academic engagement and performance (Cheung & Pomerantz, 2015). Students who see educational success as important are more likely to employ self-regulated learning strategies, set challenging goals, and persist through difficulties (Neubauer et al., 2022; Pintrich, 1999; Wang & Pomerantz, 2009). This heightened engagement has been shown to translate into improved academic outcomes over time (Alexander et al., 1997; Kenney-Benson et al., 2006; Chase et al., 2014).

Educational Stratification and Inequality in the Republic of Ireland

The Irish secondary education system is organised into two sequential phases, the Junior Cycle and the Senior Cycle, typically separated by an optional Transition Year¹. The Junior Cycle spans three years (ages 13–15) and culminates in the Junior Certificate, a national examination that strongly influences subsequent pathways. Performance in this

¹ Transition Year is an optional one-year programme that takes place after the Junior Cycle and before the two-year Leaving Certificate programme. It is designed to act as a bridge between the more structured learning of the Junior Cycle and the more self-directed learning of the Senior Cycle.

exam, alongside school-level decision-making, shapes entry into Senior Cycle programmes and determines the levels at which students can pursue core subjects such as English and Mathematics. These subjects are offered at Higher, Ordinary, or, in the case of Mathematics, Foundation level. Mathematics is a key subject because many university programmes require a Higher-level pass in it.

The Senior Cycle, normally two years in duration, offers three programmes. The Leaving Certificate Established (LCE) follows an academic curriculum, the Leaving Certificate Vocational Programme (LCVP) combines academic and vocational elements, and the Leaving Certificate Applied (LCA) provides a pre-vocational track designed for students at risk of early school leaving or with substantial educational difficulties. While LCE and LCVP students can apply directly to higher education, LCA graduates are excluded from the Central Applications Office (CAO) admissions system and typically progress into further education or the labour market. Participation in non-academic tracks is disproportionately concentrated among students from lower socio-economic backgrounds, often linked with restricted long-term educational and occupational prospects (Banks et al., 2014; Watson et al., 2006).

Access to tertiary education is centrally regulated by the CAO points system, which allocates places based on the sum of students' six best subject grade points achieved in a single sitting of the Leaving Certificate. Points vary by grade and subject level. For example, a top grade at a Higher Level carries 100 points, but a top grade at an Ordinary Level carries only 56 points. Although Ireland is frequently characterised as a "comprehensive" system (Clarke, 2010), the interaction of subject level differentiation and programme choice introduces a form of academic tracking. While less formalised than in other European contexts, these mechanisms shape educational trajectories and contribute to the reproduction of social inequalities.

Ireland has experienced a remarkable expansion of educational participation since the introduction of free post-primary schooling in 1967, following the Investment in Education report (1965). Entry into higher education rose from approximately 5% of school-leavers in the mid-1960s (Clancy, 2015) to one of the highest rates in the EU today, with 64% of 30-34-year-olds holding a third-level degree (Central Statistics Office, 2024). Irish students also perform well in international assessments, ranking second in reading and well above average in maths and science among 81 countries in the 2022 PISA (OECD, 2023). Despite this progress, persistent socio-economic disparities in access, attainment, and progression endure (Chzhen et al., 2018; Nelis & Gilleece, 2023).

Policy initiatives have attempted to address these inequalities. The Delivering Equality of Opportunity in Schools (DEIS) programme, introduced in 2005, channels resources to schools serving disadvantaged communities. The DEIS is designed to ensure that all children, regardless of their background, have access to quality education. While evaluations show gains in literacy and numeracy at the primary level (Kavanagh et al., 2017; Weir & Denner, 2013), significant achievement gaps persist, particularly between students in urban DEIS schools and their non-DEIS peers (Nelis & Gilleece, 2023). This reflects a broader reality: family socio-economic status (SES) continues to influence educational pathways, not only in determining progression but also in shaping access to curriculum quality and subject levels (Byrne & McCoy, 2017). Students from higher-SES households remain overrepresented in academic tracks and Higher-level courses, while lower-SES students are disproportionately channelled into less demanding routes (McCoy et al., 2014; McCoy & Smyth, 2011; McCoy & Byrne, 2024; Cullinan et al., 2013).

Despite the egalitarian rhetoric surrounding Irish education, expansion has not eliminated class-based disparities. Relative advantages have persisted until higher-SES participation reached saturation (Raftery & Hout, 1993; McCoy & Smyth, 2011). Moreover,

class inequalities intersect with ethnicity and race, compounding disadvantage for groups such as Travellers and immigrant-origin students (Devine, 2011; Darmody et al., 2014). Evidence increasingly challenges the notion that educational success is solely merit-based, emphasising instead the continuing influence of structural inequalities in resources, wealth, and social capital (Gilmore, 2024; Lynch & Crean, 2018).

The Current Study

Students' current academic success often reflects earlier parental expectations for future achievement—expectations that may exceed the child's performance at the time they were formed (Cheung & Pomerantz, 2015). Theoretical arguments presented earlier suggest that SES interacts with parental educational expectations (PEEs) to shape students' educational outcomes, crucially at transition points and junctures in the curriculum (Sewell & Hauser, 1972). While international research has established that SES often shapes academic trajectories via PEEs (Long & Pang, 2016) and Irish research has shown that SES significantly predicts PEEs (Smyth, 2020), the extent to which PEEs mediate the association between SES and children's track and subject-level choices remains largely unexplored in Ireland. This is important because in Ireland's educational system academic differentiation occurs through both track placement and subject-level selection, where early influences can decisively shape students' future educational and occupational trajectories.

Guided by this framework, the study advances two hypotheses. First, building on the evidence that PEEs can exert direct effects independent of family background (Sewell & Shah, 1967; Fang et al., 2018), we hypothesise that SES and early-age PEEs will each independently and positively predict students' educational outcomes when modelled concurrently, controlling for contextual factors (Independent Effects Hypothesis). Second, we propose that parental educational expectations (PEEs) measured at an earlier stage will partially mediate the relationship between socioeconomic status (SES) and students'

educational outcomes of interest (i.e., track placement and subject level differentiation), such that higher SES is associated with higher PEEs, which in turn increase the likelihood of academic track placement and selection of higher subject levels, net of contextual factors (Mediation Hypothesis).

Methods

Participants and Procedures

This study draws on data from the Child Cohort '98 of the *Growing Up in Ireland* (GUI) study, which tracks the educational, social, and developmental trajectories of a nationally representative sample of children born between November 1997 and October 1998. With approximately 8,500 participants, data were collected at multiple key stages of development including ages 9, 13, 17, 20 and most recently 25, providing a uniquely rich dataset for examining educational pathways in temporal sequence. The design of GUI, which integrates information from students, their parents or guardians, school principals, and teachers, enables a comprehensive analysis of the social, familial, and institutional factors shaping young people's academic experiences. This study used data from the GUI surveys conducted at ages 9, 13, 17, and 20, as these waves align with critical decision-making stages in the Irish education system. The first wave comprised 8,568 children and their families interviewed at age 9. As is common in longitudinal research, inter-wave attrition gradually reduced the sample size, with 6,039 participants remaining at age 17/18 and 4,729 at age 20.

Measures

Academic Attainment

Two variables were selected to represent students' attainment at the end of their secondary education: educational track (academic versus vocational) and subject level choice (ordinary versus higher level).

Educational Track. Educational track placement was measured as a binary variable distinguishing between students who followed the traditional academic Leaving Certificate and those who pursued vocationally-oriented alternatives, such as the Leaving Certificate Applied (LCA) or the Leaving Certificate Vocational Programme (LCVP). This variable was extracted from a retrospective question included in the fourth wave of the GUI, i.e., age of 20.

Subject Level Choice. The study also examined curricular differentiation through students' subject level selection in the core subjects of English and Mathematics. Subjects can be taken at Higher or Ordinary level, with Mathematics offering an additional Foundation level, worth a minimal number of CAO points or not counted at all.² These variables are reported in the third wave of the GUI (i.e., 17 years). For analytical purposes, English was represented as a binary variable distinguishing between Higher and Ordinary levels, while Mathematics was captured through a three-category measure differentiating among Higher, Ordinary, and Foundation levels.

Socioeconomic Status

Socioeconomic status (SES) was measured using two complementary indicators from earlier waves of the *Growing Up in Ireland* study: equivalised disposable household income before housing costs, categorised into quintiles, and educational attainment level of the primary caregiver, usually the mother. The income quintile measure classified households from the lowest to the highest quintile, while parental education was represented by the highest level attained by the primary caregiver, ranging from the lowest (no formal education or primary education) to the highest (postgraduate education). These measures, collected

² Irish Leaving Certificate Examination Points Calculation for college applications through the CAO (Central Applications Office) can be viewed here: <https://www.cao.ie/index.php?page=scoring&s=lcepointsgrid> .

when the child was aged 9 and 13, capture relatively stable structural resources that form the backdrop for educational decision-making.

Parental Educational Expectations

Parental educational expectations (PEEs) were operationalised as a binary variable, distinguishing between high expectations (aspiring to a college degree or higher) and lower expectations (below degree level). This variable was measured at ages 9 and 13, well before the age 17 outcomes, to ensure that expectations preceded the key academic decisions under study.

Control Variables

To account for potential confounding influences, the models incorporate a range of demographic, academic, neighbourhood, and school-level controls. Student gender is included as a binary variable (0 = male; 1 = female). Immigration background is captured through a binary indicator distinguishing whether the primary caregiver was born in Ireland (0 = yes, 1 = no). Family structure is measured by the number of co-resident siblings extracted from the second wave (age 13), entered as a continuous variable. Prior academic performance is controlled for using Junior Certificate grades in English and Mathematics, reported in the third wave of the GUI, at age 17/18. These grades are recoded into ordered categorical variables ranging from A (highest performance) to E or lower (lowest performance).

Neighbourhood context is measured using parent-reported assessments of the local area. Specifically, the availability of youth activity resources, such as sports clubs, youth centres, or swimming facilities is coded as a binary variable, with agreement indicating access to supportive resources (0) and disagreement capturing disadvantaged neighbourhood conditions (1).

School-level influences are approximated using the Delivering Equality of Opportunity in Schools (DEIS) classification, which designates schools serving populations at risk of socioeconomic disadvantage (Fleming & Harford, 2023). Because the public version of GUI does not provide unique school identifiers, DEIS status serves as the primary proxy for school socioeconomic composition. This measure is coded as a binary variable, with DEIS schools coded as 1 and non-DEIS schools coded as 0.

Analysis Plan

To estimate the relationship between SES, PEEs, and educational outcomes, two sets of statistical models were computed, distinguished by the timing of measurement for income and PEEs. In all models the dependent variables were the educational attainment variables (educational track and subject level choice) and the independent variables were equivalised household income and PEEs. In the first set of models the independent variables were measured at age 9, while in the second set of models the independent variables were measured at age 13. This dual approach allowed for the examination of whether earlier versus later parental expectations exerted different influences on subsequent academic placement and subject-level selection. Logistic regression models were used to assess the probability of academic track and English subject level choice which were both measured as binary variables. An ordered logistic regression model was applied to Mathematics subject level choice which was measured using three ordered categories (Higher, Ordinary, and Foundation). To enhance the clarity of our analysis, we included a generalized ordered logit model in addition to the regular ordered logistic (parallel-line) model. This decision served as a robustness check for our ordered outcome. This model is less sensitive to violations of the proportional odds or parallel-lines assumption, such as in rare event scenarios (Williams, 2006).

To assess the potential mediating role of parental expectations, the analysis employed the Karlson-Holm-Breen (KHB) method, which is specifically designed to decompose total effects in non-linear probability models (Karlson & Holm, 2011; Karlson et al., 2010). The KHB approach allows for the separation of direct and indirect associations, adjusting for the scale identification problem that typically arises when adding mediators to logistic regression models. This methodological refinement enabled a more accurate estimation of the extent to which the relationship between SES and educational placement was mediated by parental expectations, providing a robust test of the proposed theoretical mechanism.

Given the multicategorical nature of the SES indicators used in this study (i.e., income quintiles and parental educational levels) additional steps were taken to strengthen statistical inference regarding the mediation pathways. As Hayes and Preacher (2013) note, traditional approaches to mediation are limited in such contexts, as they rely on testing individual path coefficients and assume normality in the sampling distribution of the indirect effect. This assumption is often violated, particularly when categorical predictors are involved and the indirect effect is estimated as a product of multiple parameters, which is the case when employing the KHB method. To address these limitations, we used bootstrapped confidence intervals for the KHB indirect effects. The bootstrap provided a non-parametric means of inference that did not depend on the normality assumption, offering superior accuracy and statistical power in estimating mediation effects (Hayes & Scharkow, 2013; Hayes & Preacher, 2013). Employing this approach allowed us to perform a joint significance test for all categories of the predictor, ensuring that evidence of mediation was supported by robust statistical inference rather than individual path significance tests. This procedure enhanced the reliability of conclusions drawn about the mediating role of parental expectations in the relationship between SES and educational outcomes.

Missing Data Strategy

As with many longitudinal surveys, the GUI study is subject to inter-wave attrition, which results in varying sample sizes across waves and outcomes. Consequently, the analytic samples used for academic track placement, drawn from the fourth wave, and subject-level indicators obtained from the third wave differ in size. In addition to attrition, further reductions occurred due to missing data on key variables. The most significant sources of missingness were the outcome measures, namely, subject-level selection in English and Mathematics and track placement, as well as household income quintiles (approximately 400 missing values or 7%) and the DEIS school classification (around 450 missing cases or 8%). For the main analyses, we adopted a complete-case approach, which reduced the effective sample to roughly 4,800 observations (out of 6,039) for the subject-level models and 4,000 observations (out of 4,729) for the track placement models. To evaluate the robustness of our findings, we implemented a chained multiple imputation procedure to replace missing values in key variables and re-estimated the models, while applying longitudinal sample weights specifically designed to adjust for differential non-response. These weights, provided by the GUI research team, help ensure that the estimated relationships are not biased by systematic patterns of attrition (McNamar et al., 2021).

Results

Table 1 provides an overview of the characteristics of the larger analytical sample, specifically the one including the complete cases from waves 1-3 ($N = 4,803$), from which our variables were derived, excluding the track placement indicator. Most students (95.5%) followed the academic track at the senior cycle, consistent with the high rates of progression in Irish post-primary education. Most students completed mathematics at either Ordinary level (49.1%) or Higher level (48.4%), with only a small proportion (2.5%) taking the Foundation level. Moreover, most students achieved Higher level English (83.1%), while 16.9% completed the subject at Ordinary level. Parental education levels varied, though most

students come from households with at least post-secondary qualifications and 34.4% of parents held a bachelor's or higher degree. Household income quintiles at age 9 and 13 showed a relatively balanced distribution, with around 28% of respondents in the highest income group and less than 15% in the lowest. This deviates from the expected 20% in each quintile due to panel attrition.

Parental educational expectations were high overall, with 82.2% of parents at age 9 and 87.8% at age 13 indicating aspirations for their child to achieve a college degree.

Almost 12% of students attended schools participating in the DEIS programme (targeted at disadvantaged communities). Most students lived in neighbourhoods with available youth resources (85.4%).

The gender distribution was nearly even, and the sample was predominantly composed of children with parents born in Ireland (85.4%). Academic performance at the Junior Certificate level was broadly strong, with the majority earning B or C grades in both Mathematics and English. Lastly, the average number of siblings was approximately 1.8.

Table 1

Summary Statistics

Variables	Summary
N	4,803
Academic track (N= 4,006) *	95.5%
Leaving Certificate Level of Mathematics	
Foundation	2.5%
Ordinary	49.1%
Higher	48.4%
Leaving Certificate Level of English	
Ordinary	16.9%
Higher	83.1%
Mother's highest educational level	
None or primary	1.0%
Lower secondary	8.3%
Up sec/Postsec non-tert [†]	30.4%
Short-cycle tertiary	25.9%
Bachelor's or equivalent	19.3%
Postgraduate	15.1%
Household annual income quintiles (age 9)	
Lowest	10.3%
2nd	16.4%
3rd	19.8%
4th	24.6%

Highest	28.9%
Household annual income quintiles (age 13)	
Lowest	14.1%
2nd	15.7%
3rd	18.9%
4th	23.9%
Highest	27.5%
Parental educational expectations (age 9)	
Non-degree	17.8%
College degree	82.2%
Parental educational expectations (age 13)	
Non-degree	12.2%
College degree	87.8%
School take part in the DEIS (age 13)	
No	87.8%
Yes	12.2%
Gender	
Male	48.8%
Female	51.2%
Parent born in Ireland	
Yes	85.4%
No	14.6%
Neighborhood resources for teen's activities are available (age 13)	
Agree	76.8%
Disagree	23.2%
Number of siblings	1.806 (SD = 1.024)

Notes: * The information on track placement is collected retrospectively during the fourth wave at age 20.

Thus, it is important to note that the sample size for this outcome is smaller due to further participant attrition. †Up sec/Postsec non-tert = Upper secondary or postsecondary non-tertiary education.

SES, PEEs at Age 9, and Attainment

Table 2 presents the results (log-odds) from the regression models predicting three educational outcomes, i.e., Mathematics subject level, English subject level, and academic track placement using SES and parental educational expectations (PEEs) measured at age 9.

Across all three outcomes, clear socioeconomic gradients were observed. Students in the highest income quintile exhibited substantially higher likelihood of taking higher-level Mathematics and English compared with those in the lowest quintile, everything else being equal. Track placement also showed a statistically significant income gradient.

Parental education also strongly predicted subject-level selection and track placement, even controlling for household income. Compared to students whose parents had none or primary education, those with a parent holding a bachelor's degree or postgraduate

qualification had markedly higher odds of enrolling in the academic track and selecting higher levels in both English and Maths.

Parental educational expectations, measured at age 9, emerged as a significant predictor across all outcomes. Students whose parents expected them to attain a college degree were substantially more likely to take higher-level Mathematics and English and to follow the academic track, even after adjusting for SES and school-level factors.

At the school level, attendance at a DEIS school was associated with significantly lower likelihood of being in the academic track or taking higher-level subjects in either English and Mathematics, net of SES and PEEs. In the Mathematics model, the negative and statistically significant coefficient on gender indicated that female students were substantially less likely than male students to take Mathematics at the Higher level (relative to Ordinary or Foundation levels), while the positive and significant coefficient in the English model suggested that female students were more likely than their male peers to take English at the Higher level (relative to Ordinary). Parental immigration background, by contrast, was not statistically significantly associated with any of the outcomes, *ceteris paribus*.

Table 2.

Logistic and Ordinal Logistic Regression Analysis of Educational Outcomes with PEEs and SES Measured at Age 9

	Ordered logit	Logit	
	Mathematics level	English level	Track
Household annual income quintiles *			
2nd	0.213 (0.128)	0.224 (0.138)	0.244 (0.234)
3rd	0.423 *** (0.125)	0.544 *** (0.142)	0.798 ** (0.266)
4th	0.575 *** (0.124)	0.542 *** (0.143)	0.397 (0.257)
Highest	0.603 *** (0.127)	0.850 *** (0.156)	0.701 * (0.296)
Parent's highest educational level			
Lower secondary	0.873 * (0.354)	-0.308 (0.335)	-0.048 (0.453)
Up sec/Postsec non-tert *	1.381 ***	0.183	0.247

	(0.345)	(0.326)	(0.440)
Short-cycle tertiary	1.384 ***	0.253	0.455
	(0.348)	(0.331)	(0.458)
Bachelor's or equivalent	1.894 ***	0.520	1.018 *
	(0.352)	(0.343)	(0.516)
Postgraduate	1.842 ***	0.867 *	0.869
	(0.357)	(0.364)	(0.555)
Parental educational expectations (=1 if College degree)	0.870 ***	0.954 ***	1.004 ***
	(0.089)	(0.094)	(0.168)
School take part in the DEIS (= 1 if Yes)	-0.657 ***	-0.696 ***	-0.646 ***
	(0.104)	(0.108)	(0.127)
Gender (=1 if Female)	-0.507 ***	0.371 ***	-0.006
	(0.066)	(0.085)	(0.161)
Number of siblings	0.068 *	0.070	0.114
	(0.032)	(0.041)	(0.077)
Parent born in Ireland (= 1 if No)	0.169	-0.058	-0.273
	(0.092)	(0.120)	(0.220)
Neighborhood resources for teen's activities are available (= 1 if Disagree)	-0.020	-0.101	-0.072
	(0.076)	(0.098)	(0.183)
Junior Certificate's Math grade			
B	-0.354 ***	-0.141	-0.295
	(0.106)	(0.159)	(0.345)
C	-1.166 ***	-0.313 *	-0.489
	(0.109)	(0.160)	(0.343)
D	-1.913 ***	-0.445 **	-0.550
	(0.130)	(0.172)	(0.362)
E or lower	-2.582 ***	-0.963 **	-0.855
	(0.306)	(0.309)	(0.577)
Junior Certificate's English grade			
B	-0.446 ***	-0.669 ***	-0.484 *
	(0.109)	(0.190)	(0.419)
C	-0.877 ***	-0.787 ***	-0.925 **
	(0.109)	(0.189)	(0.409)
D	-1.080 ***	-1.496 ***	-1.395 **
	(0.138)	(0.204)	(0.429)
E or lower	-0.888 *	-2.053 *	-1.798 **
	(0.389)	(0.420)	(0.687)
Number of observations	4798	4803	4006

Notes: * Up sec/Postsec non-tert = Upper secondary or postsecondary non-tertiary education.

‡ Reference groups for income and parental education are respectively the lowest quintile and none or primary. ***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05

SES, PEEs at Age 13, and Attainment

Table 3 summarises the results from regression models predicting three key educational outcomes, i.e., Mathematics subject level, English subject level, and academic track placement using SES and parental educational expectations (PEEs) measured at age 13.

Patterns across the three outcomes revealed persistent and sizeable socioeconomic gradients. Students from the highest quintile showed consistently higher likelihood of achieving higher-level placement in Mathematics and English, as well as being enrolled in the academic track, compared with students from the lowest quintile. Students whose parents held a bachelor's degree or higher had substantially greater likelihood of entering the academic track and taking higher-level English and Mathematics compared to those whose parents had only primary education or no formal education.

Parental educational expectations at age 13 were strongly and positively associated with all three outcomes. Students whose parents aspired for them to complete a college degree were significantly more likely to take higher-level subjects and to follow the academic track, net of SES and school-level controls. Relative to the age 9 models, the PEE effects at age 13 are slightly stronger. For instance, the average marginal effect of PEE at age 13 on academic track placement and English subject-level choice was 0.07 ($p < 0.001$) and 0.20 ($p < 0.001$), respectively, compared with 0.05 ($p < 0.001$) and 0.14 ($p < 0.001$) when expectations were measured at age 9. We illustrated the marginal effects associated with key predictors of age-specific models in Figures A1-A3 as supplemental materials.

Attending a DEIS school continued to be associated with significantly lower chances of advanced subject-level placement and academic tracking, even after adjusting for SES and PEEs. This finding could highlight the enduring impact of concentrated school disadvantage on educational opportunities. A persistent gendered pattern of curricular differentiation was also observed where female students were more strongly positioned in English but disadvantaged in Mathematics at the point of subject-level selection.

Table 3.

Logistic and Ordinal Logistic Regression Analysis of Educational Outcomes with PEEs and SES Measured at Age 13

	Ordered logit	Logit	
	Mathematics level	English level	Track

Household annual income quintiles *			
2nd	0.263 *	0.463 ***	0.001
	(0.118)	(0.136)	(0.227)
3rd	0.392 ***	0.530 ***	0.050
	(0.115)	(0.136)	(0.238)
4th	0.398 ***	0.540 ***	0.778 **
	(0.112)	(0.135)	(0.277)
Highest	0.732 ***	0.781 ***	0.744 *
	(0.117)	(0.152)	(0.312)
Parent's highest educational level			
Lower secondary	0.830 *	0.403	0.257
	(0.354)	(0.340)	(0.447)
Up sec/Postsec non-tert †	1.309 ***	0.768 *	0.641
	(0.344)	(0.328)	(0.434)
Short-cycle tertiary	1.316 ***	0.875 **	0.813
	(0.346)	(0.333)	(0.449)
Bachelor's or equivalent	1.821 ***	1.180 ***	1.089 *
	(0.350)	(0.344)	(0.495)
Postgraduate	1.821 ***	1.655 ***	1.032
	(0.355)	(0.367)	(0.536)
Parental educational expectations (= 1 if College degree)	1.222 ***	1.293 ***	1.327 ***
	(0.110)	(0.103)	(0.171)
School take part in the DEIS (= 1 if Yes)	-0.659 ***	-0.706 ***	-0.481 *
	(0.104)	(0.111)	(0.189)
Gender (= 1 if female)	-0.496 ***	0.375 ***	-0.046
	(0.066)	(0.087)	(0.160)
Number of siblings	0.061	0.064	0.109
	(0.033)	(0.043)	(0.078)
Parent born in Ireland (= 1 if No)	0.161	-0.080	-0.256
	(0.092)	(0.121)	(0.218)
Neighborhood resources for teen's activities are available (= 1 if Disagree)	-0.021	-0.100	-0.026
	(0.076)	(0.100)	(0.184)
Junior Certificate's Math grade			
B	-0.349 **	-0.151	-0.450
	(0.107)	(0.161)	(0.359)
C	-1.128 ***	-0.311	-0.488
	(0.109)	(0.162)	(0.361)
D	-1.891 ***	-0.427 *	-0.590
	(0.130)	(0.176)	(0.380)
E or lower	-2.373 ***	-0.808 *	-1.128 *
	(0.302)	(0.317)	(0.551)
Junior Certificate's English grade			
B	-0.482 ***	-0.703 ***	-0.559
	(0.110)	(0.194)	(0.417)
C	-0.898 ***	-0.779 ***	-0.849 *
	(0.110)	(0.194)	(0.411)
D	-1.118 ***	-1.484 ***	-1.320 **
	(0.139)	(0.209)	(0.430)
E or lower	-1.067 **	-2.013 ***	-1.547 *
	(0.396)	(0.425)	(0.685)
Number of observations	4740	4748	3971

Notes: † Up sec/Postsec non-tert = Upper secondary or postsecondary non-tertiary education.

* Reference groups for income and parental education are respectively the lowest quintile and none or primary. ***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05.

Mediation Analysis Using the KHB Method

Tables 4 and 5 report the bootstrapped indirect effects of socioeconomic status (SES) on students' educational outcomes through parental educational expectations (PEEs), along with corresponding bootstrap standard errors and joint significance test p-values. We also reported evidence of strong positive associations between SES measures and PEEs in Figure A4 as well as the non-bootstrapped (standard) KHB decomposition results in Tables A1 and A2 in the supplemental materials. The bootstrap procedure did not alter the original point estimates derived from the sample data but substantially improved the precision of the estimates by reducing standard errors and tightening confidence intervals. As a result, several indirect effects that were marginal or non-significant in the standard models became statistically distinguishable from zero.

When PEEs were measured at age 9 (Table 4), statistically significant indirect effects emerged primarily for higher parental education groups and the top income quintiles. Specifically, the indirect effects associated with the highest income category were positive and significant across all three outcomes. The indirect effects of parental education increased monotonically with educational attainment, reaching their highest values among parents with bachelor's ($\beta = 0.310-0.371$, all $p < .001$) and postgraduate qualifications ($\beta = 0.333-0.387$, all $p < .001$). The joint significance tests confirmed the overall mediation effect for both income ($p = 0.000-0.003$) and education ($p < .001$), indicating that early parental expectations at age 9 serve as a meaningful pathway linking family SES to educational outcomes.

When SES and PEEs were measured later, at age 13 (Table 5), the pattern of mediation remained relatively unchanged. The indirect effects associated with household income were obvious across all outcomes. In particular, the indirect effects were positive and statistically significant for the top three income quintiles across mathematics level, English level, and track placement. Similarly, the indirect effects associated with parental education

were also significant at 5% significance level among parents with bachelor's or postgraduate qualifications. Overall, the joint tests remained highly significant for both SES indicators ($p < .001$), underscoring the overall robustness of the indirect pathways, particularly the enduring importance of parental expectations as channels through which household income and parental education continue to shape educational positioning in adolescence.

Table 4.

Bootstrap KHB indirect results of influence of SES through PEEs (at age 9) and joint significance test results.

	Maths level	English level	Track
Income quintile			
<i>2nd</i>	-0.007 (0.023)	0.000 (0.023)	0.019 (0.028)
<i>3rd</i>	0.003 (0.021)	0.005 (0.022)	0.034 (0.028)
<i>4th</i>	0.027 (0.020)	0.033 (0.021)	0.069 * (0.029)
<i>Highest</i>	0.060 ** (0.021)	0.067 ** (0.022)	0.098 *** (0.030)
Joint significance test (P-value)	0.000	0.000	0.003
Education			
<i>Lower secondary</i>	0.095 (0.069)	0.102 (0.072)	0.122 (0.082)
<i>Upsec/Postsec non-tert</i> †	0.198 ** (0.069)	0.215 ** (0.073)	0.230 ** (0.084)
<i>Short-cycle tertiary</i>	0.241 *** (0.071)	0.264 *** (0.074)	0.295 *** (0.089)
<i>Bachelor's or equivalent</i>	0.310 *** (0.074)	0.338 *** (0.077)	0.371 *** (0.095)
<i>Postgraduate</i>	0.333 *** (0.075)	0.364 *** (0.078)	0.387 *** (0.097)
Joint significance test (P-value)	0.000	0.000	0.000
N	4798	4803	4006

Notes: † Up sec/Postsec non-tert = Upper secondary or postsecondary non-tertiary education. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$

Table 5.

Bootstrap KHB indirect results of influence of SES through PEEs (at age 13) and joint significance test results.

	Math level	English level	Track
Income quintile			

<i>2nd</i>	0.018 (0.027)	0.019 (0.028)	-0.009 (0.031)
<i>3rd</i>	0.081 *** (0.025)	0.085 *** (0.025)	0.061 * (0.029)
<i>4th</i>	0.088 *** (0.024)	0.089 *** (0.025)	0.066 * (0.029)
<i>Highest</i>	0.125 *** (0.024)	0.130 *** (0.025)	0.116 *** (0.030)
Joint significance test (P-value)	0.000	0.000	0.000
Education			
<i>Lower secondary</i>	-0.048 (0.084)	-0.053 (0.091)	-0.007 (0.097)
<i>Upsec/Postsec non-tert</i> †	0.075 (0.078)	0.081 (0.087)	0.101 (0.093)
<i>Short-cycle tertiary</i>	0.124 (0.081)	0.132 (0.088)	0.165 (0.096)
<i>Bachelor's or equivalent</i>	0.178 * (0.080)	0.189 * (0.087)	0.224 * (0.098)
<i>Postgraduate</i>	0.186 * (0.081)	0.199 * (0.088)	0.227 * (0.098)
Joint significance test (P-value)	0.000	0.000	0.000
N	4798	4803	4006

Notes: † Up sec/Postsec non-tert = Upper secondary or postsecondary non-tertiary education. ***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05

Following Karlson, Holm, and Breen (2012), it is often more informative to examine the average marginal effects of mediation paths across models, as these provide a clearer interpretation of effect sizes in probabilistic terms. However, because the user-written KHB package in Stata does not currently support formal statistical testing for marginal effects or bootstrapped standard errors, we were unable to obtain bootstrapped estimates for these quantities. Given that the point estimates from our sample regressions and the bootstrapped models were identical, we report the average marginal effects derived from the sample regressions as reliable approximations.

The average marginal effects of all KHB indirect paths are presented in Figures 1–3. These results reveal distinct patterns by both the timing of measurement and the type of SES indicator. At age 9, the marginal effects of indirect paths of parental education were consistently larger than those observed at age 13, suggesting that early parental expectations more effectively transmit the influence of parental education on students' academic outcomes

through PEEs. For instance, the grey squares in Figure 1, which represent the average marginal effects of the indirect paths from parental education to the likelihood of taking higher-level Mathematics, are visibly larger in the left panel (age 9) than in the right panel (age 13). In contrast, the pattern for household income differed slightly: the average marginal effects of income-related indirect paths were stronger at age 13 than at age 9, particularly in the models predicting Mathematics and English subject-level selection. In other words, the relative magnitude of indirect effects associated with parental education and household income gradually converged over time, reflecting a developmental shift in the mechanisms through which different dimensions of SES shape educational decision-making through PEEs.

Figure 1. Marginal Effects of Age-Specific KHB Indirect Paths of SES on the Likelihood of Each Mathematics Level

Figure 2. Marginal Effects of Age-Specific KHB Indirect Paths of SES on the Likelihood of Higher English Level

Figure 3. Marginal Effects of Age-Specific KHB Indirect Paths of SES on the Likelihood of Academic Track Placement

Robustness checks

Our generalized ordered logit models for the choice of Mathematics subject levels closely resembled the results from our standard ordered logistic models. This consistency is evident when we compare the patterns of average marginal effects shown in Figure A3 (standard ordered logit) with those reported in Figure A5 (generalized ordered logit) included in supplemental materials. Additional robustness checks also yielded results highly consistent with the complete-case models. Estimates from the weighted models with imputed datasets closely mirrored those obtained from the original logistic and ordered logistic regressions, as well as from the KHB mediation analyses (Tables A3-A4 and Figures A6-A10 of supplemental materials). The direction, magnitude, marginal effects, and significance of the main coefficients remained mostly stable across specifications, indicating that neither inter-wave attrition nor missingness in key variables substantially biased the findings. These similarities reinforce the validity of the complete-case approach adopted in the main and bootstrap analyses and lend further confidence to the robustness of the observed associations between SES, parental expectations, and educational outcomes.

Discussion

This study set out to understand how socioeconomic status (SES) and parental educational expectations (PEEs) intersect to shape educational pathways in the Irish secondary system. The findings strongly indicate that SES and PEEs operate both independently and jointly, producing clear gradients in track placement and subject level selection. These results contribute to several strands of theoretical and empirical research on educational inequality.

From a theoretical standpoint, the independent and mediating influence of PEEs reinforces classic formulations within the status attainment tradition. The Wisconsin Model positions parental expectations as a central mechanism through which family background influences children's academic outcomes (Sewell & Hauser, 1972; Sewell et al., 1969). The significant effects of PEEs observed here, net of SES, prior achievement, and school context, support the argument that expectations are not simply proxies for socioeconomic resources but instead reflect an active socialising process that shapes students' orientations, persistence, and decision making (Pinguart & Ebeling, 2020; Wang & Pomerantz, 2009). At the same time, the fact that PEEs do not fully mediate SES effects aligns with evidence that structural inequalities remain deeply entrenched and cannot be neutralised by psychological or motivational processes alone (Li et al., 2020; Fang et al., 2018).

The pattern of partial mediation observed for both parental education and income is also consistent with theories of effectively maintained inequality (Lucas, 2001). Even within a nominally comprehensive education system, advantaged families secure qualitatively superior educational opportunities for their children by navigating curricular differentiation, especially in core subjects such as English and Mathematics. Irish research has shown that these subtle forms of tracking, particularly the distinction between higher and lower difficulty levels, play a decisive role in maintaining class-based inequalities in access to higher education (Byrne & McCoy, 2017; Smyth, 2018). The present findings reinforce this evidence by demonstrating that children from higher SES families are systematically more likely to take Higher level subjects and follow academic tracks, even when achievement and school level factors are controlled.

The slightly stronger associations between expectations measured at age 13 and educational outcomes also merit consideration. Psychological theories suggest that expectations may become more realistic and more closely aligned with forthcoming decisions

as students approach critical branching points (Cheung & Pomerantz, 2015; Yamamoto & Holloway, 2010). Expectations formed at this stage may therefore exert greater behavioural influence, especially in a system where subject level choices for the Leaving Certificate begin to crystallise in early adolescence. The persistent influence of expectations at both ages indicates that early parental signals matter long before students formally enter the Senior Cycle.

The educational implications of these findings are substantial. The strong and consistent influence of PEEs suggests that parents' beliefs and aspirations represent meaningful intervention points. Existing research demonstrates that parental involvement and value communication contribute to children's academic engagement and achievement, particularly during adolescence (Grolnick & Slowiaczek, 1994; Hill & Tyson, 2009). Yet Irish studies show that parents vary widely in their understanding of subject level consequences for CAO eligibility and long-term trajectories (McCoy et al., 2014). This informational asymmetry may contribute to divergence in expectations and, consequently, to unequal academic positioning.

Additionally, the results indicate that early adolescence is a particularly consequential period during which expectations become tightly connected to curricular decisions. Strengthening parental engagement, communication, and guidance during this period may help mitigate socioeconomic gradients in subject level choice. Moreover, the independent associations between SES and expectations suggest that interventions aimed at fostering high but realistic parental expectations will be effective only if accompanied by systemic measures addressing resource disparities, school level disadvantage, and uneven access to high level curricula.

Policy implications follow directly from these findings. The Irish education system has expanded access significantly since the introduction of free post primary education, yet

structural inequalities persist (Clancy, 2015; Clancy, 2024). The continuing significance of SES status for academic placement indicates that policy efforts targeting school level disadvantage remain essential. Evaluations of DEIS highlight that while improvements have been achieved, inequalities in retention, progression, and access to Higher level subjects endure (Kavanagh et al., 2017; Nelis & Gilleece, 2023). Enhancing resource allocation, guidance counselling provision, and supports for mixed ability teaching in disadvantaged schools may therefore help reduce the inequalities documented here.

Furthermore, the complexity of subject level choices within the Leaving Certificate system underscores the need for greater transparency and standardised guidance for students and parents. Research consistently shows that families with lower SES possess less information about the implications of lower versus higher level subjects, which may shape their expectations and, ultimately, their children's choices (Finger, 2016; Zhan & Sherraden, 2011). Strengthened national communication strategies and earlier guidance interventions could therefore reduce socioeconomic disparities in curricular positioning.

Finally, because parental expectations constitute a meaningful but incomplete pathway to academic opportunities, policy initiatives must address both psychological and structural mechanisms. Supporting parent-school partnerships, enhancing early guidance, and reducing inequalities in school resources work best when pursued simultaneously. This aligns with broader discussions about equity within Irish education and the need to ensure that curricular differentiation does not reproduce social stratification under the guise of choice (Lynch & Crean, 2018). However, these educational policies operate within a broader context of income inequality and the redistributive capacity of the tax-benefit system.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that parental expectations and socioeconomic background jointly shape educational outcomes in Ireland through both direct and indirect pathways.

Parental expectations, even when measured early in childhood, exert significant influence on students' academic trajectories and partly mediate SES effects. Yet the persistent direct effects of SES highlight the limits of expectation-based mechanisms in addressing structural disadvantage. These findings illustrate how family level processes and institutional arrangements interact to produce enduring inequalities in access to higher level curricula and academic tracks.

The study contributes to ongoing debates about how inequalities are reproduced within a system that is formally comprehensive but substantively differentiated. It suggests that policies aimed at enhancing parental engagement, improving the clarity of subject choice processes, and strengthening supports for disadvantaged schools could mitigate some of the inequalities observed. However, it also emphasises that expectations alone cannot overcome structural barriers rooted in socioeconomic resources and school contexts. A sustained commitment to equity driven policy, informed by longitudinal evidence such as that presented here, remains vital if Ireland is to provide genuinely equal opportunities for all students.

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Supplementary Materials

Figure A1. Marginal Effects of Age-Specific SES and PEEs on the Likelihood of Each Math Subject-level (ordered logit)

Figure A2. Marginal Effects of Age-Specific SES and PEEs on the Likelihood of Higher English Level (logit)

Figure A3. Marginal Effects of Age-Specific SES and PEEs on the Likelihood of Academic Track Placement (logit)

Figure A4. Marginal Effects of Age-Specific Effects of SES on PEEs (logit)

Table A1.

KHB mediation regression results with parental expectation as the mediator (PEEs and SES measured at age 9).

Variables	Math level	English level	Track
Income quintile			
<i>2nd</i>			
Total	0.206	0.065	0.263
Direct	0.213	0.065	0.244
Indirect	-0.007	0.000	0.019
<i>3rd</i>			
Total	0.425 ***	0.550 ***	0.832 **
Direct	0.423 ***	0.544 ***	0.798 **
Indirect	0.003	0.005	0.034
<i>4th</i>			
Total	0.602 ***	0.575 ***	0.465
Direct	0.575 ***	0.542 ***	0.397
Indirect	0.027	0.033	0.069
<i>Highest</i>			
Total	0.663 ***	0.918 ***	0.800 **
Direct	0.603 ***	0.850 ***	0.701 *
Indirect	0.060	0.067	0.098
Education			
<i>Lower secondary</i>			
Total	0.969 *	-0.206	0.073
Direct	0.873 *	-0.308	-0.048

Indirect	0.095	0.102	0.122
<i>Upsec/Postsec non-tert</i> [†]			
Total	1.580 ***	0.398	0.477
Direct	1.381 ***	0.183	0.247
Indirect	0.198	0.215	0.230
<i>Short-cycle tertiary</i>			
Total	1.625 ***	0.518	0.750
Direct	1.384 ***	0.253	0.455
Indirect	0.241	0.264	0.295
<i>Bachelor's or equivalent</i>			
Total	2.204 ***	0.858 *	1.390 **
Direct	1.984 ***	0.520	1.118 *
Indirect	0.310 *	0.338 *	0.371 *
<i>Postgraduate</i>			
Total	2.175 ***	1.231 ***	1.256 *
Direct	1.842 ***	0.867 *	0.869
Indirect	0.333 *	0.364 *	0.387 *
N	4798	4803	4006

Notes: † Up sec/Postsec non-tert = Upper secondary or postsecondary non-tertiary education. ***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05

Table A2.

KHB mediation regression results with parental expectation as the mediator (PEEs and SES measured at age 13).

Variables	Math level	English level	Track
Income quintile			
<i>2nd</i>			
Total	0.281 *	0.482 ***	-0.008
Direct	0.263 *	0.463 ***	0.001
Indirect	0.018	0.019	-0.009
<i>3rd</i>			
Total	0.472 ***	0.615 ***	0.112
Direct	0.392 ***	0.530 ***	0.050
Indirect	0.081	0.085	0.061
<i>4th</i>			
Total	0.486 ***	0.629 ***	0.843 **
Direct	0.398 ***	0.540 ***	0.778 **
Indirect	0.088	0.089	0.066
<i>Highest</i>			
Total	0.857 ***	0.911 ***	0.860 **
Direct	0.732 ***	0.781 ***	0.744 *
Indirect	0.125	0.130	0.116
Education			
<i>Lower secondary</i>			
Total	0.781 *	0.350	0.250
Direct	0.830 *	0.403	0.257
Indirect	-0.048	-0.053	-0.007
<i>Upsec/Postsec non-tert</i> [†]			
Total	1.385 ***	0.848 **	0.741

Direct	1.309 ***	0.768 *	0.641
Indirect	0.075	0.081	0.101
<i>Short-cycle tertiary</i>			
Total	1.439 ***	1.007 **	0.987 *
Direct	1.316 ***	0.875 **	0.813
Indirect	0.124	0.132	0.165
<i>Bachelor's or equivalent</i>			
Total	1.999 ***	1.369 ***	1.312 **
Direct	1.821 ***	1.180 ***	1.1089 *
Indirect	0.178	0.189	0.224
<i>Postgraduate</i>			
Total	2.007 ***	1.854 ***	1.256 *
Direct	1.821 ***	1.655 ***	1.032
Indirect	0.186	0.199	0.227
N	4740	4748	3971

Notes: † Up sec/Postsec non-tert = Upper secondary or postsecondary non-tertiary education. ***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05

Figure A5. Marginal Effects of Age-Specific SES and PEEs on the Likelihood of Each Math Subject-level (general ordered logit)

Figure A6. Regression results of SES and PEEs at Age 9 on Educational Outcomes with Imputed Data and Attrition Weights

Figure A7. Regression results of SES and PEEs at Age 13 on Educational Outcomes with Imputed Data and Attrition Weights

Table A3.

Bootstrap KHB indirect results of influence of SES through PEEs (at age 9) and joint significance test results with weighted and imputed data.

	Maths level	English level	Track
Income quintile			
<i>2nd</i>	0.026 (0.021)	0.030 (0.023)	0.051 (0.030)
<i>3rd</i>	0.043 * (0.020)	0.048 * (0.023)	0.072 * (0.029)
<i>4th</i>	0.073 *** (0.020)	0.082 *** (0.023)	0.105 *** (0.031)
<i>Highest</i>	0.106 *** (0.021)	0.119 *** (0.024)	0.140 *** (0.032)
Joint significance test (P-value)	0.000	0.000	0.000
Education			
<i>Lower secondary</i>	0.085 (0.056)	0.096 (0.063)	0.072 (0.079)
<i>Upsec/Postsec non-tert</i> †	0.218 *** (0.057)	0.245 *** (0.064)	0.219 ** (0.080)
<i>Short-cycle tertiary</i>	0.278 *** (0.058)	0.312 *** (0.066)	0.293 *** (0.085)
<i>Bachelor's or equivalent</i>	0.359 *** (0.061)	0.403 *** (0.069)	0.387 *** (0.091)
<i>Postgraduate</i>	0.374 *** (0.062)	0.420 *** (0.070)	0.395 *** (0.091)
Joint significance test (P-value)	0.000	0.000	0.000
N	6003	6003	4704

Notes: † Up sec/Postsec non-tert = Upper secondary or postsecondary non-tertiary education. ***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05

Table A4.

Bootstrap KHB indirect results of influence of SES through PEEs (at age 13) and joint significance test results with weighted and imputed data.

	Math level	English level	Track
Income quintile			
<i>2nd</i>	0.019 (0.022)	0.020 (0.024)	0.009 (0.029)
<i>3rd</i>	0.076 *** (0.022)	0.079 *** (0.023)	0.074 * (0.029)

<i>4th</i>	0.094 *** (0.021)	0.098 *** (0.022)	0.091 *** (0.028)
<i>Highest</i>	0.130 *** (0.021)	0.135 *** (0.023)	0.133 *** (0.030)
Joint significance test (P-value)	0.000	0.000	0.000
Education			
<i>Lower secondary</i>	-0.005 (0.076)	-0.005 (0.080)	-0.004 (0.097)
<i>Upsec/Postsec non-tert</i> †	0.132 (0.073)	0.138 (0.076)	0.117 (0.094)
<i>Short-cycle tertiary</i>	0.189 * (0.074)	0.197 * (0.077)	0.196 * (0.096)
<i>Bachelor's or equivalent</i>	0.251 *** (0.075)	0.262 *** (0.077)	0.257 ** (0.098)
<i>Postgraduate</i>	0.262 *** (0.075)	0.274 *** (0.077)	0.263 ** (0.099)
Joint significance test (P-value)	0.000	0.000	0.000
N	5922	5922	4646

Notes: † Up sec/Postsec non-tert = Upper secondary or postsecondary non-tertiary education. ***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05

Figure A8. Marginal Effects of Age-Specific KHB Indirect Paths of SES on the Likelihood of Higher Mathematics Level with Imputed Data and Attrition Weights

Figure A9. Marginal Effects of Age-Specific KHB Indirect Paths of SES on the Likelihood of Higher English Level with Imputed Data and Attrition Weights

Figure A10. Marginal Effects of Age-Specific KHB Indirect Paths of SES on the Likelihood of Academic Track Placement with Imputed Data and Attrition Weights